

THE INFLUENCE OF SERVANT LEADERSHIP, COMPETENCY, EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATIONS AND WORK ENVIRONMENT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE MEDIATED BY JOB SATISFACTION

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Abstract

Performance shows the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee after carrying out the work tasks given by the organization. Employee performance are influenced by servant leadership, competence, educational qualifications and work environment. This study aims to examine the influence of servant leadership, competency, educational qualifications and work environment on employee performance is mediated by job satisfaction. This research was conducted at the Regional Office X of the State Civil Service Agency with Civil Servants as research subjects. Regional Office X, what is interesting is that researchers are interested in choosing this place because apart from the employees of Regional Office. Another thing that researchers are interested in conducting research at this office is to explore the influence of various factors that influence organizational performance besides the influence of the work environment. The research population this time are all Civil Servants who worked at the Regional Office X of the State Civil Service Agency totaling 89 people. The number of samples used in this research was 89 people using the saturated sample method because the number of employees is below 100, all employees are used as a sample. Researchers carried out data collection techniques in this research through the results of distributing questionnaires. Questionnaires were distributed to Civil Servants of Regional Office X State Civil Service Agency through by google form with a Likert scale of 1-10. The analysis technique used is Partial Least Squares (PLS). The results show that Servant Leadership has a positive effect on job satisfaction, Servant Leadership has a positive effect on employee performance, Job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance, Competency has a positive effect on employee performance, Competency has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, Education Qualifications have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction, However Education Qualifications have a negative effect on employee performance, The work environment has a positive effect on job satisfaction, The work environment has a positive effect on employee performance, Servant Leadership has a positive effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediator, Competence has a positive effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediator, Educational qualifications influence employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediator, and The work environment has a positive effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediator.

Keywords: Servant Leadership, Competency, Educational Qualifications, Work Environment, Performance, Job Satisfaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Based on Ministerial Regulation for Empowerment of State Civil Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform No. 88 of 2021 concerning Evaluation of Performance Accountability of Government Agencies, it is clear regarding how Government Agencies develop strategies to achieve predetermined performance targets in accordance with established rules.

Referring to the Letter of the Minister for Empowerment of State Civil Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform No.B/ 704 /AA.05/2022 Dated December 6 2022 concerning the Results

of the 2022 Evaluation of the Performance Accountability of Government Agencies (AKIP) of the State Civil Service Agency, the results of the evaluation of the performance accountability of the State Civil Service Agency show a score of 68.48 with the predicate "B" indicating that implementation of performance accountability is "good", which means that AKIP is implemented well at the institutional level and in several main work units.

However, this still requires improvement and commitment to performance management. And there has been no significant increase in the AKIP score for the State Civil Service Agency in 2021 which received a score of 68.05. This also happened at the Regional Office the following is a table of Performance Accountability values at Regional Office X of the State Civil Service Agency taken from the AKIP TA report. 2023: And based on the State Property (BMN) asset management report of the Regional Office This is related to the capital expenditure budget at the Regional Office

In the current era, we are the age of competence, the winners in this era are those who are able to compete and have the ability and skills. As time goes by in implementing Government Regulation no. 11 of 2017 concerning ASN Management has experienced many new changes or transformations in ASN governance in Indonesia, one of which is ASN Development, including planning, recruitment processes, appointments and promotions in career development, where this emphasizes three absolutely important things, namely: qualifications, competence, and performance.

Furthermore, employee competency levels will certainly become stricter as time goes by. The level of employee education can improve the performance of a company or organization and increase its competitiveness (Sabban, 2018). Of course, a higher level of education is very necessary in the world of more capable organizational competitiveness.

In other words, the employee's performance will increase as a result of the skills, expertise and dexterity he shows while working for a company or government agency. Therefore, it is necessary to plan, implement and evaluate human resources so that they can exploit other resources available by work units in work units and even companies by considering their own needs and paying more special attention in prioritizing all the needs of employees or subordinates who are expected to always be achieve organizational or company performance goals.

Certain factors can influence the successful performance of government agencies, one of which is human resources. Human resources are responsible for all planning and evaluation processes, and have the ability to empower other resources that are assets of the company or work unit to improve employee performance. Employee performance will ultimately correlate with organizational or agency performance.

Leadership influences organizational performance, especially with dynamic leadership replacement. Servant leadership, which is known as Servant Leadership, emphasizes a leader's ability to serve his employees so that they can have a good influence on employees without making them afraid or reluctant towards the employees' superiors. Servant leadership behavior is important for employees to provide motivation or work enthusiasm.

This leader does not prioritize his own needs, instead he prioritizes all the needs of his employees or subordinates to improve performance as is the expected goal of the work unit or company and pays attention to employee job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction can be defined as a combination of various emotions, values, and perceptions that a person has about the responsibilities related to their job. The expected level of job satisfaction can help employees achieve company goals and improve their performance at work.

The job satisfaction factor is of course related to employee performance: the more satisfied employees are with work in their field, the more satisfied employees are with the results they have achieved.

In achieving an employee's performance, it cannot be separated from the work environment, because the work environment is a place to achieve the target goals of their work. A decent, comfortable and safe working environment that is able to provide what employees need is expected to provide a sense of satisfaction and stimulate their work enthusiasm.

The work environment even becomes a source of sharing information and a place or forum for carrying out all activities, so the company provides conducive work environment conditions so that employees feel worthy, satisfied and comfortable indoors or outdoors in completing work. A conducive work environment will have an influence on improving the quality of an employee's performance and will also have an impact on the effectiveness of activities as well as high efficiency of time and resources.

The results of research conducted by Pala'langan (2021) prove that Servant Leadership has no impact on employee job satisfaction. Research conducted by Adiputra et al. (2017) proves that competency actually has a positive, although not significant, impact on company performance.

Apart from that, the results of research conducted by Sundari et al. (2023) shows that, based on direct observations made by the author in January 2023, there are civil servants working at the Pasaman Regency Regional Financial Agency who do not have the competence, expertise and understanding of translating several orders given by their superiors.

Meanwhile, research conducted by Sinambela (2020) states that achieving job satisfaction is also hampered if a person's competencies cannot be applied to the right place and job according to their field of expertise. In research conducted by Suharno et al. (2023) stated that educational qualifications do not have a significant impact on performance. In the research results of Kardiasih et al. (2017) proves that the work environment has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance.

The results of this research are in line with what Hanafi et al (2017) stated that the work environment does not have a significant influence on employee performance. This is further strengthened by the results of research conducted by Nurhandayani (2022) which proves that the work environment has an impact, although not significant, on employee performance. However, research conducted by Rastana et al. (2021), proves that the physical work environment has a partially positive and significant impact on employee performance.

Plus the research support of Martini et al. (2022) stated that the work environment has a positive and very significant impact on job satisfaction. Previous research stated that servant leadership had no influence on employee job satisfaction, Competence has a positive and insignificant effect on company performance, educational qualifications do not have a significant effect on performance and the work environment has proven that it has an impact, although not significant, on employee performance.

From the various journals that have been read, researchers have not found research that examines the effect of educational qualifications on employee performance through job satisfaction and in previous research separately only examined three different variables and no one has examined the four simultaneously, namely servant leadership, competency, and qualification variables education and work environment on performance with job satisfaction as a mediating variable.

This research is important to test and prove how the results of the influence between servant leadership, competence, educational qualifications and work environment on employee performance are mediated by job satisfaction, especially to know and proved the results of the mediating effect of job satisfaction on educational qualifications on employee performance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Employee Performance

According to Silaen (2021; 1) Performance is the work results achieved by someone in completing their responsibilities. Performance can also be defined as a person's level of success in completing an overall task within a certain time period.

Completion of tasks and responsibilities by a group of people in an organization can also be defined as performance because employees need assessment as feedback after achieving targets, assessments must be made to monitor employee performance. Performance is something that is very important for organizations in achieving performance goals which have become a common target (Fachrezi & Khair, 2020).

2.2 Servant Leadership

The main factor that greatly influences how well an organization achieves its goals is human resources (HR). Where employee performance is one of the factors that influences the company (Regen, Johannes, Edward, Yacob, 2020).

Every organization or office must have the ability to compete in the current era of globalization in order to survive in the global market. One element that influences human resources is leadership.

Leadership should provide motivation to employees to strive for good performance (Monga, Coetzee, Cilliers, 2012). One important aspect of leadership is the relationship a leader has with his employees or followers.

2.3 Competency

In the opinion of Assoc Prof. Dedi Rianto Rahadi (2021) states that "Competency" is the knowledge, skills, abilities and behavior used by an employee when carrying out their duties at work. Competence is very important for employees to achieve results that are in accordance with the company's business strategy.

Competence, according to McClelland in Zainal (2015), is an important attribute that every individual or employee has, which influences or can predict performance well. According to Boyatzis in Donni Juni Priansa (2017), competence is the ability possessed by individuals or employees that will enable them to fulfill their job requirements in a company so that the company can achieve the expected results

2.4 Educational Qualifications

Educational qualifications are special education that is obtained to obtain the abilities needed to carry out certain tasks or occupy certain positions. According to Mulyadi (2015:101) One of the factors that influences work productivity is the level of education. A higher level of education will make work easier for employees, meaning they are more productive.

Atutuli (2017:6) says that educational qualifications are closely related to a person's level of education, and that the higher a person's education level, the higher the productivity or performance of the workforce, which can improve the company's performance and increase its competitiveness in the business world in which it is involved

2.5 Work Environment

The work environment includes what is around employees and influences how they carry out their tasks (Darmadi, 2020). Examples of work environments include air conditioning, good lighting, and others. The work environment is all the tools and materials used where someone works and the settings in which they work, both individually and in groups (Prasetyo, 2021).

In addition, as stated by Latif et al. (2022), the work environment is the place where employees carry out their daily work. A safe work environment will provide a sense of security to employees, which in turn will increase their ability to do their best work.

If the work environment is good and meets employee needs, such as having adequate facilities and infrastructure and harmonious working relationships between fellow employees and superiors, it will be a comfortable and conducive work environment.

2.6 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction can be defined as a person's perception, feeling, or attitude towards his or her job, as well as its relationship to the work environment, type of work, compensation, coworkers, and social relationships at work. Job satisfaction is when someone fulfills some of their wants and needs through their work. Some employees will have different levels of job satisfaction. Different job satisfaction is also influenced by different social statuses in society.

According to Spector (2022), job satisfaction is a person's evaluation of their field of work as a whole, including job aspects such as salary, work environment and opportunities for development.

Meanwhile, Hackman and Oldham (2022) view job satisfaction as a positive feeling that arises when individuals feel actively involved in their work and feel that their work provides added value and satisfaction. According to the theory of behavior control (theory of planned behavior) there are two categories of behavior control.

The first is controlling covert behavior (cover behavior) and the second is controlling open behavior (overt behavior). The main aim is to organize and put various forms of behavioral control into perspective.

Based on reviews of relevant literature and previous research, the research model utilized in this study can be described as:

Fig 1: Theoretical Framework

This study has formulated the hypotheses based on the literature research and figures before;

- H₁:** Servant Leadership has a positive effect on job satisfaction
- H₂:** Servant Leadership has a positive effect on employee performance
- H₃:** Job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance
- H₄:** Competency has a positive effect on job satisfaction,
- H₅:** Competency has a positive effect on employee performance
- H₆:** Qualifications have a positive effect on job satisfaction
- H₇:** Qualifications have a positive effect on employee performance
- H₈:** The work environment has a positive effect on job satisfaction
- H₉:** The work environment has a positive effect on employee performance
- H₁₀:** Servant Leadership has a positive effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediator
- H₁₁:** Competence has a positive effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediator,
- H₁₂:** Educational qualifications influence employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediator,
- H₁₃:** The work environment has a positive effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediator

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted at the Regional Office X of the State Civil Service Agency with Civil Servants as research subjects. Regional Office What is interesting is that researchers are interested in choosing this place because apart from the employees of Regional Office Another thing that researchers are interested in conducting research at this office is to explore the influence of various factors that influence organizational performance besides the influence of the work environment.

The research population this time was all Civil Servants who worked at the Regional Office X of the State Civil Service Agency totaling 89 people. The number of samples used in this research was 89 people using the saturated sample method because the number of employees is below 100, all employees are used as a sample (population research).

Researchers carried out data collection techniques in this research through the results of distributing questionnaires. Distribution of the questionnaire was carried out using a Google form at the Civil Servants Regional Office X National Civil Service Agency.

Questionnaires were distributed to Civil Servants of Regional Office X State Civil Service Agency with a Likert scale of 1-10. This research is a type of quantitative research. In this

research, quantitative data is score data resulting from distributing questionnaires which are then processed using Smart PLS statistical software, namely Structural Equation Modeling Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) version 4.0 (Salisu, 2020)

Table 1: Variables and Indicators

Variables	Definition	Indicators
Employee Performance (Y2)	Defined as the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in accordance with the job responsibilities given to him (Mangkunegara in Budiyanto 2020)	1. Quality 2. Quantity 3. Timeliness 4. Effectiveness Independence Source: Robbin in Budiyanto (2020)
Job satisfaction (Y1)	Hackman and Oldham (2022) view job satisfaction as a positive feeling that arises when individuals feel actively involved in their work and feel that their work provides added value and satisfaction.	1. Salary and Compensation 2. Leadership management 3. Career Opportunities. 4. The Work Itself. 5. Company Policy Source: Paul E. Spector (2022)
Servant Leadership (X1)	Greenleaf in Nugraha et al (2023) Servant leadership covers issues such as ethics, customer experience, role modeling, and motivation and employee involvement.	1. Affection (Love) 2. Empowerment 3. Vision (Vision) 4. Humility 5. Trust (Trust) Source: Dennis in Nugraha et al (2023)
Competence (X2)	Assoc Prof. Dedi Rianto Rahadi (2021) states that "Competency" is the knowledge, skills, abilities and behavior used by an employee when carrying out their duties at work.	1. Proactive 2. Dare to Take Risks. 3. Future Oriented. 4. Knowledge and Skills Source: Adiputra (2017)
Educational Qualification (X3)	Atutuli (2007:6) Educational qualifications are a person's individual level of education with special education which will influence their productivity or performance.	1. Education level 2. Educational Suitability. Source: Mulyadi (2015)
Work environment (X4)	The work environment is all the tools and materials used where someone works and the settings in which they work, both individually and in groups (Prasetyo, 2021).	1. Working Atmosphere 2. Colleague Relations 3. Air Circulation 4. Noise. 5. Facilities Source: Nitisemito (2019)

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1) *Convergent validity*

To analyze the research model, the Partial Least Square (PLS) method was used with the SmartPLS 4.0 M3 program tool. There are two basic model evaluations in this test, namely the outer model and the inner model. *Convergent validity* with reflexive indicators it can be seen from the correlation between scores indicator with variable scores. Individual indicators are considered reliable if they have a correlation value above 0.50. The results of the correlation between dimensions and variables can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 2: Results of Convergent Validity Testing (Outer Loading)

	X1	X2	X3	X4	Y1	Y2
X1.1	0.891					
X1.2	0.814					
X1.3	0.868					
X1.4	0.825					
X1.5	0.902					
X2.1		0.799				
X2.2		0.799				
X2.3		0.822				
X2.4		0.858				
X2.5		0.833				
X3.1			0.899			
X3.2			0.884			
X4.1				0.865		
X4.2				0.860		
X4.3				0.852		
X4.4				0.789		
X4.5				0.821		
Y1.1					0.848	
Y1.2					0.855	
Y1.3					0.856	
Y1.4					0.866	
Y1.5					0.840	
Y2.1						0.883
Y2.2						0.900
Y2.3						0.879
Y2.4						0.909
Y2.5						0.910

Source: Processed data, 2024

Analysis results *Convergent Validity* Table 1 shows that all indicators have values *Outer Loading* more than 0.7 so it is declared that the research instrument has passed *Convergent Validity*. Another method for assessing convergent validity is to look at the average variance extracted (AVE) value for each variable. A model that has convergent validity is said to be achieved if it has an AVE value greater than 0.5. The AVE results are listed in Table 2

Table 2: Results of Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variables	Average variance extracted (AVE)
X1. (Servant Leadership)	0.741
X2. (Competence)	0.776
X3. (Educational Qualification)	0.795
X4. (Work environment)	0.702
Y1. (Job satisfaction)	0.728
Y2. (Employee Performance)	0.803

Source: Primary data processed, 2024

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that all variables have an Average variance extracted (AVE) value of more than 0.50. So it is stated that all the variables studied in the research model have met convergent validity and the variables used are valid.

2) Discriminant validity

The discriminant validity test is assessed based on *cross loading* measurement with the construction. The discriminant validity value is greater than 0.7, then the latent variable is a good comparison for the model. As for the test results *discriminant validity* Latent variable correlation can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity Test Results (Cross Loading)

	X1	X2	X3	X4	Y1	Y2
X1.1	0.891	0.649	0.614	0.634	0.690	0.699
X1.2	0.814	0.689	0.563	0.563	0.632	0.562
X1.3	0.868	0.566	0.621	0.627	0.637	0.648
X1.4	0.825	0.564	0.639	0.568	0.654	0.621
X1.5	0.902	0.591	0.551	0.625	0.652	0.701
X2.1	0.546	0.799	0.586	0.700	0.734	0.617
X2.2	0.539	0.799	0.702	0.631	0.684	0.600
X2.3	0.593	0.822	0.667	0.735	0.797	0.683
X2.4	0.598	0.858	0.591	0.722	0.729	0.721
X2.5	0.632	0.833	0.818	0.813	0.777	0.692
X3.1	0.643	0.722	0.899	0.713	0.785	0.718
X3.2	0.592	0.738	0.884	0.676	0.769	0.630
X4.1	0.643	0.782	0.635	0.865	0.827	0.769
X4.2	0.688	0.732	0.633	0.860	0.827	0.858
X4.3	0.639	0.764	0.777	0.852	0.841	0.784
X4.4	0.476	0.720	0.603	0.789	0.635	0.574
X4.5	0.433	0.676	0.604	0.821	0.643	0.569
Y1.1	0.595	0.722	0.675	0.768	0.848	0.747
Y1.2	0.687	0.819	0.664	0.764	0.855	0.813
Y1.3	0.644	0.763	0.713	0.818	0.856	0.772
Y1.4	0.672	0.795	0.836	0.751	0.866	0.782
Y1.5	0.637	0.765	0.827	0.796	0.840	0.725
Y2.1	0.632	0.711	0.632	0.774	0.782	0.883
Y2.2	0.682	0.698	0.698	0.762	0.780	0.900
Y2.3	0.673	0.735	0.661	0.763	0.810	0.879
Y2.4	0.713	0.725	0.703	0.758	0.814	0.909
Y2.5	0.674	0.750	0.700	0.818	0.848	0.910

Source: Primary data processed, 2024

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that all latent variable correlation discriminant validity values for each variable are greater than 0.7 and have higher values compared to other latent variables. Thus, it can be concluded that in the second stage of testing all indicators met the discriminant validity requirements.

3) Composite reliability

Besides testing validity, a reliability test of variables was also carried out which was measured using two criteria, namely composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha from the indicator block that measured the variables. A variable is declared reliable if the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values are above 0.70. The output results can be seen in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Composite Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)
X1. (Servant Leadership)	0.912	0.915	0.935
X2. (Competence)	0.880	0.882	0.913
X3. (Educational Qualification)	0.742	0.745	0.886
X4. (Work environment)	0.895	0.906	0.922
Y1. (Job satisfaction)	0.907	0.907	0.930
Y2. (Employee Performance)	0.939	0.939	0.953

Source: Primary data processed, 2024

Results output composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha for all research variables are all above 0.70. Thus, it can be explained that all the variables tested were declared reliable so they could be analyzed further.

Evaluation of the structural model or inner model

Testing of the structural model or inner model in this research consists of the R-square value test (R²), Predictive Relevance test (Structural Q²), model fit test, Effect Size (f-Square) test and Hypothesis Testing which can be seen from the path coefficient results. The evaluation results of the structural model or inner model are explained respectively as follows:

1) R-square value (R²)

In this structural model, there are three endogenous variables, namely: Job Satisfaction (Y1) and Employee Performance (Y2). The coefficient of determination (R²) for this research can be presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5: R-square value

Model Structural	Dependent Variable	R-square	Adjusted R-square
1	Y1. (Job satisfaction)	0.839	0.829
2	Y2. (Employee Performance)	0.917	0.914

Source: Primary data processed, 2024

Based on Table 5, model influence of servant leadership, competence, educational qualifications, and work environment on job satisfaction gives an R-square value of 0.839 which can be interpreted that the Job Satisfaction variable can be explained by variability servant leadership, competence, educational qualifications, and work environment amounting to 83.9 percent, while the remaining 16.1 percent is explained by other variables outside those studied. Next, the influence model servant leadership, competence, educational qualifications,

work environment and job satisfaction with employee performance gives an R-square value of 0.917 which can be interpreted that the variability of the Employee Performance variable can be explained by the variability of the Servant Leadership, Competency, Work Environment and Job Satisfaction variables of 91.7 percent, while the remaining 8.3 percent is explained by other variables outside those studied.

2) Predictive Relevance (Structural Q2)

To measure how well the observed values are produced by the model and also the estimated parameters, it is necessary to calculate Q-square. The Q-square value has a value range of $0 < Q^2 < 1$, where the closer to 1 means the model is better. Predictive Relevance calculation results are calculated using blindfolding with the following output:

Table 6: Test Results Predictive Relevance (Structural Q2)

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Y1. (Job satisfaction)	445.000	183.133	0.588
Y2. (Employee Performance)	445.000	130.254	0.707

Source: Primary data processed, 2024

Table 6 shows that the Q-square value for the job satisfaction variable is 0.588, so it can be concluded that the model has good predictive relevance. Thus, it can be explained that the influence model servant leadership, competence, educational qualifications, and work environment on job satisfaction has good relevant predictive ability with a predictive ability value of 58, 8%. The Q-square value for the employee performance variable is 0.707 so it can be concluded that the model has good predictive relevance. Thus, it can be explained that the influence model servant leadership, competence, educational qualifications, and work environment on job satisfaction has good relevant predictive ability with a predictive ability value of 70.7%.

3) F - Square (f2) Test Results

The effect size f2 measures the impact of a particular predictor construct on the endogenous construct. This measure is used to evaluate whether the predictor construct if removed will have a large impact on the R-Square values of the endogenous constructs. A guide to assessing f2 values for exogenous latent constructs in predicting endogenous constructs. The f-Square category is divided into three, namely 0.02 is a weak influence, 0.15 is a medium influence, and 0.35 is a strong influence (Ghozali, 2021:75).

Table 7: Output f Square

	(Job satisfaction)	(Employee Performance)
X1. (Servant Leadership)	0.060	0.077
X2. (Competence)	0.235	0.273
X3. (Educational Qualification)	0.286	0.015
X4. (Work environment)	0.406	0.072
Y1. (Job satisfaction)		0.267
Y2. (Employee Performance)		

Source: Data Processed Results, 2024

Based on table 7, it can be concluded that the results of testing the effects between research variables are as follows:

- a) The Servant Leadership variable (X1) has an F-Square value of 0.060 which is in the F-Square criteria between 0,15 s.d > 0,02 which means that Servant Leadership has a weak effect or impact on Job Satisfaction (Y1).
- b) The Servant Leadership variable (X1) has an F-Square value of 0.077 which is in the F-Square criteria between 0,15 s.d > 0,02 which means that Servant Leadership has a weak effect or impact on Employee Performance (Y2).
- c) The Competency variable (X2) has an F-Square value of 0.235 which is in the F-Square criteria between 0.35 to > 0.15 which means that competence has a moderate effect or impact on Job Satisfaction (Y1).
- d) The Competency variable (X2) has an F-Square value of 0.273 which is in the F-Square criteria between 0.35 to > 0.15 which means that competence has a moderate effect or impact on Employee Performance (Y2).
- e) The Educational Qualification variable (X3) has an F-Square value of 0.286 which is in the F-Square criteria between 0.35 to > 0.15, which means that educational qualifications have a moderate effect or impact on Job Satisfaction (Y1).
- f) The Educational Qualification variable (X3) has an F-Square value of 0.015 which is in the F-Square criteria between 0,15 s.d > 0,02 which means that educational qualifications have a weak effect or impact on Employee Performance (Y2).
- g) The Work Environment variable (X4) has an F-Square value of 0.406 which is in the F-Square criteria > 0.35 which means that the Work Environment has a strong effect or impact on Job Satisfaction (Y1).
- h) The Work Environment variable (X4) has an F-Square value of 0.072 which is in the F-Square criteria between 0,15 s.d > 0,02 which means that the Work Environment has a weak effect or impact on Employee Performance (Y2).
- i) The Job Satisfaction variable (Y1) has an F-Square value of 0.267 which is in the F-Square criteria between 0.35 to > 0.15, which means that Job Satisfaction (Y1) has a moderate effect or impact on Employee Performance (Y2).

Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis testing is carried out using a t-test by dividing it into testing direct influence and indirect influence or testing mediating variables. In the following section, the results of direct influence testing and mediating variable testing are described respectively.

Direct Effect Testing

This research uses a Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis approach to test the research hypothesis that was stated previously. The results of the empirical research model analysis using Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis can be seen in Figure 2 below.

Fig 2: Inner Model

The results of the path coefficient validation test on each path for direct influence can be presented in Table 8 below

Table 8: Direct Effect Testing Results (Path Coefficient)

	Relationship Between Variables	Path Coefficient (Bootstrapping)	T Statistics	P Value	Information
H1	X1. (Servant Leadership) → Y1. (Job satisfaction)	0,106	2,178	0,030	H1 accepted
H2	X1. (Servant Leadership) → Y2. (Employee Performance)	0,172	2,764	0,017	H2 accepted
H3	Y1. (Job Satisfaction) → Y2. (Employee Performance)	0,723	4,593	0,000	H3 accepted
H4	X2. (Competency) → Y1. (Job Satisfaction)	0,250	2,646	0,008	H4 accepted
H5	X2. (Competency) → Y2. (Employee Performance)	0,270	2,318	0,000	H5 accepted
H6	X3. (Educational Qualification) → Y1. (Job Satisfaction)	0,282	3,467	0,001	H6 accepted
H7	X3. (Educational Qualification) → Y2. (Employee Performance)	-0,103	1,033	0,288	H7 rejected
H8	X4. (Work Environment) → Y1. (Job satisfaction)	0,399	4,449	0,000	H8 accepted
H9	X4. (Work Environment) → Y2. (Employee Performance)	0,279	2,078	0,017	H9 accepted

Source: Data Processed Results, 2024

Information from Table 8, the results of hypothesis testing can be determined which are presented in the following description:

1. Servant Leadership proven to have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction. This result is shown by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.106 with a t-statistic of 2,178 (t-statistic > 1.96) and has a p value of 0.030 <0.050, thus, hypothesis 1 (H1) can be proven. The results obtained can be interpreted as meaning that the better the implementation of servant leadership, the more employee job satisfaction will increase.
2. Servant Leadership proven to have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This result is shown by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.172 with a t-statistic of 2.764 (t-statistic > 1.96), and has a p value of 0.017 <0.050, thus, hypothesis 2 (H2) can be proven. The results obtained can be interpreted to mean that the better the implementation of servant leadership, the more employee performance will increase.
3. Job satisfaction has been proven to have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This result is shown by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.723 with a t-statistic of 4.593 (t-statistic > 1.96), and has a p value of 0.000 <0.050, thus, hypothesis 3 (H3) can be proven. The results obtained can be interpreted as meaning that the higher job satisfaction felt by employees, will make better the performance produced by employees.
4. Competency has been proven to have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. This result is shown by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.250 with a t-statistic of 2.646 (t-statistic > 1.96), and has a p value of 0.008 <0.050, thus, hypothesis 4 (H4) can be proven. The results obtained can be interpreted as follows, improved the competency better an employee has, the employee job satisfaction will also increase too.
5. Competency has been proven to have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This result is shown by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.270 with a t-statistic of 2.318 (t-statistic > 1.96), and has a p value of 0.000 <0.050, thus, hypothesis 5 (H5) can be proven. The results obtained can be interpreted as follows the better the competency an employee has, the greater the employee's sense of performance will increase.
6. Educational qualifications have been proven to have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction. This result is shown by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.282 with a t-statistic of 3.467 (t-statistic > 1.96), and has a p value of 0.001 >0.050, thus, hypothesis 6 (H6) can be proven. The results obtained can be interpreted as follows the better the educational qualifications an employee has, the employee job satisfaction will increase.
7. Educational qualifications have been proven to have a negative and do not significant effect on Employee Performance. This result is shown by the path coefficient which has a negative value of -0.103 with a t-statistic of 1.033 (t-statistic < 1.96), and has a p value of

0.288 > 0.050, thus, hypothesis 7 (H7) can be rejected. The results obtained can be interpreted as follows; the better the educational qualifications an employee has, it doesn't make employee performance will increase.

8. Work Environment is proven to have a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction. This result is shown by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.399 with a t-statistic of 4.449 (t-statistic > 1.96), and has a p value of 0.000 < 0.050, thus, hypothesis 8 (H8) can be proven. The results obtained can be interpreted to mean that the better the work environment to be provide, the greater the employee's sense of job satisfaction.
9. The work environment has been proven to have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This result is shown by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.279 with a t-statistic of 2.078 (t-statistic > 1.96), and has a p value of 0.017 < 0.050, thus, hypothesis 9 (H9) can be proven. The results obtained can be interpreted to mean that the better the work environment to be provided, the more employee performance will increase.

Indirect Effect Testing

The testing of the indirect influence hypothesis in this research can be described in Table 9 below:

Recapitulation of Indirect Effect Testing Results

Relationship Between Variables	Path Coefficient (Bootstrapping)	T-Statistics	P-Values	Information
<i>Servant leadership</i> (X ₁) → Job Satisfaction (Y ₁) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)	0,077	2,061	0,040	Positive Significant
Competency (X ₂) → Job Satisfaction (Y ₁) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)	0,180	2,351	0,019	Positive Significant
Educational Qualifications (X ₃) → Job Satisfaction (Y ₁) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)	0,204	2,630	0,009	Positive Significant
Work Environment (X ₄) → Job Satisfaction (Y ₁) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)	0,288	2,939	0,003	Positive Significant

Source: Data Processed Results, 2024

Based on 9 above, the indirect effect can be explained as follows:

- 1) The effect of servant leadership (X1) on employee performance (Y2) through job satisfaction (Y1) is positive with a path coefficient value of 0.077 with a t-statistic value of 2.061 greater than the t-table of 1.963 and has a p-value of 0.040 < 0.050 which means that job satisfaction mediates the effect of servant leadership on employee performance so that the tenth hypothesis (H10) is accepted.
- 2) The effect of competence (X2) on employee performance (Y2) through job satisfaction (Y1) is positive with a path coefficient value of 0.180 with a t-statistic value of 2.351 greater than the t-table of 1.963 and has a p-value of 0.019 < 0.050 which means that job satisfaction mediates the effect of competence on employee performance so that the eleventh hypothesis (H11) is accepted.

- 3) The effect of educational qualifications (X3) on employee performance (Y2) through job satisfaction (Y1) is positive with a path coefficient value of 0.204 with a t-statistic value of 2.630 greater than the t-table of 1.963 and has a p-value of 0.009 < 0.050, which means that job satisfaction mediates the effect of servant leadership on employee performance so that the twelfth hypothesis (H12) is accepted.
- 4) The effect of work environment (X4) on employee performance (Y2) through job satisfaction (Y1) is positive with a path coefficient value of 0.288 with a t-statistic value of 2.061 greater than the t-table of 1.963 and has a p-value of 0.003 < 0.050, which means that job satisfaction mediates the effect of work environment on employee performance so that the thirteenth hypothesis (H13) is accepted.

Indirect Effect Testing (Examination of Mediation Variables)

Examination of mediating variables in this research will examine the mediating role of Job Satisfaction on indirect effects *Servant Leadership*, Competency, Educational Qualifications, and Work Environment on Employee Performance. The examination of indirect effects in this research can be seen in the explanation of the analysis results in Table 10 as follows.

Table 10: Recapitulation of Mediation Variable Test Results

Mediation Variables	Path Coefficient	T-Statistics	Mediation Information
<i>Servant leadership</i> (X ₁) → Job Satisfaction (Y ₁) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)			
<i>Servant leadership</i> (X ₁) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)	0,172	2,764	<i>Partial mediation</i> (Weaken)
<i>Servant leadership</i> (X ₁) → Job Satisfaction (Y ₁) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)	0,077	2,061	
Competency (X ₂) → Job Satisfaction (Y ₁) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)			
Competency (X ₂) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)	0,270	2,318	<i>Partials mediation</i> (Strengthen)
Competency (X ₂) → Job Satisfaction (Y ₁) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)	0,180	2,351	
Educational Qualifications (X ₃) → Job Satisfaction (Y ₁) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)			
Educational Qualifications (X ₃) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)	-0,103	1,033	<i>Full mediation</i>
Educational Qualifications (X ₃) → Job Satisfaction (Y ₁) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)	0,204	2,630	
Work Environment (X ₄) → Job Satisfaction (Y ₁) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)			
Work Environment (X ₄) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)	0,279	2,078	<i>Partials mediation</i> (Strengthen)
Work Environment (X ₄) → Job Satisfaction (Y ₁) → Employee Performance (Y ₂)	0,288	2,939	

Source: Data Processed Results, 2024

Based on the criteria in examining the mediation effect, then from table 10 above, information can be obtained as presented in the following explanation:

- 1) Based on Table 10 above, it shows that the path coefficient value is 0.172 and the t-statistic value is 2.764 > 1.963 for the direct relationship between servant leadership and employee performance. This means that the servant leadership variable on employee performance has a positive and significant effect (direct effect). However, it turns out that the relationship

between servant leadership and employee performance mediated by job satisfaction has a significant effect. This can be seen from Table 10 above that the path coefficient value is 0.077 and the t-statistic value is above 1.963, namely 2.061, which means significant. Because when the mediating variable, namely job satisfaction, is included in the direct relationship between servant leadership and employee performance, it is significant. then the job satisfaction variable acts as partial mediation. Because the value of the path coefficient and t-statistic after the mediating variable is lower, it shows that the mediating variable of job satisfaction weakens the effect of servant leadership on employee performance. So, it can be represented that job satisfaction as a partial mediation variable weakens the relationship. Based on these results it can be interpreted that Employee Performance can be further increased if Servant Leadership is implemented the better and the employees have a feeling high Job Satisfaction, so that in the end employee performance will increase.

- 2) Based on Table 10 above, it shows that the path coefficient value is 0.270 and the t-statistic value is $2.318 > 1.963$ for the direct relationship between competence and employee performance. This can be interpreted that the competency variable on employee performance has a positive and significant effect (direct effect). However, it turns out that the relationship between competence and employee performance mediated by job satisfaction has a significant effect. This can be seen from Table 10 above that the path coefficient value is 0.180 and the t-statistic value is above 1.963, namely 2.351, which means significant. Because when the mediating variable, namely job satisfaction, is included in the direct relationship between competence and employee performance, it is significant, the job satisfaction variable acts as a partial mediation. Because the value of the path coefficient and t-statistic after the mediating variable is higher, it shows that the mediating variable of job satisfaction strengthens the effect of competence on employee performance. So, it can be represented that job satisfaction is a partial mediation variable that strengthens the relationship. Job Satisfaction is able to mediate partially (strengthens) on the influence of Competency on Employee Performance. It's can be interpreted that Employee Performance can increase if employees have sufficient competency the better and the employees have a feeling high Job Satisfaction, so that in the end employee performance will increase.
- 3) Job satisfaction is able to positively mediate the indirect influence of perceived educational qualifications on employee performance. These results are shown from the mediation tests carried out, based on Table 10 above, it shows that the path coefficient value is -0.103 and the t-statistic value is $1.033 < 1.963$ for the direct relationship between educational qualifications and employee performance. This means that the educational qualification variable has no effect on employee performance. However, it turns out that the relationship between educational qualifications and employee performance mediated by job satisfaction has a significant effect. This can be seen from Table 10 above that the path coefficient value is 0.204 and the t-statistic value is above 1.963, namely 2.630, which means significant. Because when the mediating variable, namely job satisfaction, is included in the direct relationship between educational qualifications and employee performance, it is significant.

Then the job satisfaction variable acts as a full mediation. Because in the initial relationship (direct effect) of educational qualifications to employee performance that has no effect but after the mediating variable there is a significant relationship from educational qualifications to employee performance. So, it can be represented that job satisfaction is a full mediation variable. On these results it can be interpreted that Employee Performance can increase further if employees have the better adequate educational qualifications and the employees have a feeling high Job Satisfaction, so that in the end employee performance will increase

- 4) Job satisfaction is able to positively mediate the indirect influence of the work environment on employee performance. These results are shown from the mediation tests carried out, based on Table 10 above, it shows that the path coefficient value is 0.279 and the t-statistic value is $2.078 > 1.963$ for the direct relationship between work environment and employee performance. This means that the work environment variable on employee performance has a positive and significant effect (direct effect). However, it turns out that the relationship between work environment and employee performance mediated by job satisfaction has a significant effect. This can be seen from Table 10 above that the t-statistic value is above 1.963, namely 2.939, which means significant. Because when the mediating variable, namely the job satisfaction media, is included in the direct relationship between the work environment and employee performance, it is significant. Then the job satisfaction variable acts as a full mediation. Because the value of the path coefficient and t-statistic after the mediating variable is higher, it shows that the mediating variable of job satisfaction strengthens the effect of the work environment on employee performance. So, it can be represented that job satisfaction is a partial mediation variable that strengthens the relationship. On these results it can be interpreted that Employee Performance can increase if employees accept the conditions of the working environment better and the employees have a feeling high Job Satisfaction, so that in the end employee performance will increase

5. CONCLUSIONS

The better implementation of servant leadership, the more employee job satisfaction will increase and also better the implementation of servant leadership, the more employee performance will increase. In same case, the higher job satisfaction felt by employees, will make better the performance produced by employees. When talk about competency, an improved the competency better an employee has, the employee job satisfaction will also increase too and then the better the competency an employee has, the greater the employee's sense of performance will increase. As we know that people want to achieve education to improve their competence and quality of life. So, the better the educational qualifications an employee has, the employee job satisfaction will increase. However, in this research even though the better the educational qualifications an employee has, it doesn't make employee performance will increase. The better the work environment to be provide, the greater the employee's sense of job satisfaction and then the better the work environment to be provided, the more employee performance will increase. In this research, when talk about in examining the mediation effect, Employee Performance can be further increased if Servant Leadership is implemented the better and the employees have a feeling high Job Satisfaction, so that in the

end employee performance will increase. Employee Performance can increase if employees have sufficient competency the better and the employees have a feeling high Job Satisfaction, so that in the end employee performance will increase. Employee Performance can increase further if employees have adequate educational qualifications the better and the employees have a feeling high Job Satisfaction, so that in the end employee performance will increase. Employee Performance can increase if employees accept the conditions of the working environment better and the employees have a feeling high Job Satisfaction, so that in the end employee performance will increase.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to express our thanks to all parties who have helped complete this study. Therefore, on this occasion the author would like to express my deepest gratitude to I Gede Merta and Ni Ketut Tambun as the author's parents who continuously provide support and prayers to the author. As well as other parties who have helped and accompanied me in the process of working on this research. And thanks to all friends of MM 63 Undiknas who always accompanied me in the process of completing this thesis

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